

EVALUATION OF SEXUAL DIMORPHISM USING PALPEBRAL FISSURE DIMENSIONS IN ASARI-TORU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

Sexual dimorphism in facial morphology plays a critical role in forensic identification, clinical assessment, and anthropometric research. This study examined sexual dimorphism in palpebral fissure parameters among adults in Asari-Toru Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. A total of 412 participants (192 males and 220 females) aged 18–60 years were assessed using standard anthropometric techniques. The mean palpebral fissure width (PFW) was 32.17 ± 2.79 mm in males and 32.04 ± 2.97 mm in females; palpebral fissure height (PFH) 9.48 ± 1.49 mm and 9.51 ± 1.56 mm; palpebral angle $16.47 \pm 2.73^\circ$ and $16.62 \pm 2.88^\circ$; inner canthal distance (ICD) 34.69 ± 3.33 mm and 34.04 ± 2.89 mm; and outer canthal distance (OCD) 98.51 ± 6.07 mm and 97.75 ± 5.87 mm, respectively. Independent t-tests and ANOVA revealed that only ICD showed a statistically significant sex difference ($p = 0.034$), while other parameters showed no significant variation with sex or age ($p > 0.05$). Logistic regression analysis indicated limited predictive power of palpebral measurements for sex determination (Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.02$; classification accuracy = 54.9%). These findings suggest that ICD may serve as an auxiliary marker in forensic and anthropometric evaluations; however, palpebral fissure dimensions alone are insufficient for reliable sex classification. The study highlights the importance of establishing population-specific reference standards for facial morphometry in African populations.

KEYWORDS: Sexual Dimorphism, Palpebral Fissure Dimensions, Forensic Identification, Anthropometry, Inner Canthal Distance (ICD), Asari-Toru LGA.

INTRODUCTION

Anthropometry, the scientific discipline concerned with the measurement and proportion of the human body, dates to the 19th century. Key figures such as Adolph Quetelet, a Belgian astronomer and statistician, and Alphonse Bertillon, a French police officer, laid the groundwork for its forensic and biometric applications.^[1] Facial anthropometry has been widely used to study morphological variation across populations. In Nigerian populations, studies have provided baseline data on cephalofacial indices among children, highlighting

population-specific craniofacial patterns critical for forensic and clinical applications.^[2] This gap hinders accurate medical diagnostics, ergonomic design, and biometric system calibration in the African context.^[3] Most anthropometric studies emphasize the length and width of the palpebral fissure, yet the inclination (the upward or downward slant of the fissure) also carries clinical and diagnostic importance, influencing perceptions of age, health, and symmetry in facial aesthetics.^[4] Biological sex represents the genotype while gender is the phenotype of the individual. Sex is

the biological characterization of sexually reproducing species based on reproductive roles and attributes, that is shown to exhibit inter and intra population variability.^[5] Sex determination is the process of differentiation and development of the undifferentiated gonads toward the ovaries or the testis.^[6]

Sex determination is an important aspect of anthropometry since it helps in the reconstruction of the biological profile of unidentified individuals. The previously used traditional methods for this examination and identification of individuals in previous times have been proven to be very ineffective, and they rely on parameters that can be affected by some confounding factors such as age, ancestry and individual variability and parameters include dental and skeletal analysis. Studies have shown that palpebral fissure dimensions exhibit sexual dimorphism, with males generally having larger palpebral fissures than females, its ease of measurement and convenience and its non-invasive nature unlike skeletal and dental analysis which involves invasive procedures.^[7] The palpebral fissure refers to the elliptical opening between the upper and lower eyelids. It plays a key role in facial aesthetics and is functionally significant in protecting the eye and regulating tear distribution. The dimensions of the palpebral fissure, including its width, height, and intercanthal distances, have been studied for their variations between males and females across different populations. Given the impact of genetic, hormonal, and environmental factors on craniofacial development, these variations can serve as useful indicators for sex determination.^[8,9]

Facial morphology has gained attention as a potential tool for sex estimation, with features such as the nasal region, jawline, and eye structures being analyzed for sexual dimorphism. Among these, the palpebral fissure has been suggested as a possible indicator of sex differences. Research indicates that factors such as genetic inheritance, hormonal influences, and ethnic background contribute to variations in palpebral fissure dimensions, yet the extent of these variations and their reliability for sex determination remain underexplored.^[8,10] There is a growing need to establish sex-specific standards for biometric identification in Nigeria. Given that genetic and environmental factors influence facial morphology, population-specific studies are crucial for improving the accuracy of anthropometric databases. In most African populations, sexual determination using palpebral fissures have been underexplored despite the advancements in clinical medicine and forensic anthropology. The aim of this study is to investigate the sex-based differences in palpebral dimensions among individuals in Asari-Toru LGA. The specific objectives are to measure palpebral fissure dimensions (length, height, inter-canthal distance, and inclination) across age groups and sexes, assess the statistical significance of these differences, and develop a predictive model for sex determination.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional observational study design was utilized. A total of 412 participants were analyzed, comprising 192 males (46.6%) and 220 females (53.4%). Participants were aged between 18 and 60 years old.

Inclusion criteria

Male and female adults (18-60yrs old), Indigenous and long-term residents of Asari-Toru LGA, Individuals with no history of ocular or facial surgeries and Participants who provided informed verbal consent.

Exclusion criteria

Children and elderly individuals (below 18 and above 60yrs) avoid developmental and age-related changes in facial morphology. Individuals with facial deformities, trauma or any medical condition that may alter the palpebral fissure dimensions. People wearing contact lenses or undergoing eye treatments that may alter the palpebral fissure dimensions.

Sample size and its determination

To determine an appropriate sample size for this study on sex determination using palpebral fissures in Asari-Toru LGA, we will use Taro Yamene's,^[11] formula for sample size calculation:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 * p * (1-p)}{E^2}$$

Where:

- n_0 = required sample size
- Z = Z-score (1.96 for 95% confidence level)
- p = estimated proportion of the population with the characteristic of interest (if unknown, use 0.5 for maximum variability)
- e = margin of error (typically 5% or 0.05)

Calculation

Substituting the values:

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 * 0.5 * (1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n_0 = 383$$

The calculated sample size is approximately 384 participants. Based on the 2006 Nigerian National Population Census, Asari-Toru Local Government Area (LGA) had a population of 219,787.

To determine the appropriate sample size for this study on sex determination using palpebral fissures, using the finite population correction formula:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + (n_0 - 1/N)}$$

Where:

- n = adjusted sample size
- n_0 = initial sample size (384)
- N = total population (219,787)

Substituting these values

$$n = \frac{384}{1 + (383/219,787)}$$

$$n = \frac{384}{1 + 0.001742}$$

$$n = \frac{384}{1.001742}$$

$$n = 383.33$$

$$\text{unadjusted} = 384 \times 1.07 = 412$$

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The sample size was adjusted to account for missing measurements, data errors and non-response.

Ethical Considerations

Inner Canthal Distance (ICD): distance between the inner corner of both eyes.

Fig 1 showing the inner canthal distance (labelled 2).^[13]

1= Inter papillary distance

2= Inner canthal distance

3= Palpebral fissure width

Outer Canthal Distance (OCD)- distance between the outer corners of the eyes.

Ethical research approval was obtained from the research committee of the faculty of basic medical sciences. The consent form was obtained for the respondents. The confidentiality information of the respondents was ensured and kept safe, and the participants had the right to end participation at any time, following the human subjects' rights enacted by the National Institute of Justice, U.S.A in 2010.

Measurement Techniques

Data collection followed standardized anthropometric techniques. All measurements were obtained using a digital vernier caliper to ensure precision. Stratified sampling method was used to ensure representation of different sexes and age groups.

Fig. 2: Showing the outer canthal distance.^[14]

- OCD= outer canthal distance
- IPD= inter-papillary distance
- ICD= inner canthal distance

Palpebral Fissure Height (PFH)- vertical height of the eye opening.

Fig. 3: Showing the palpebral fissure height.^[14]

- PFH= palpebral fissure height
- PFW= palpebral fissure width
- PFI= palpebral fissure inclination

Palpebral Fissure Width (PFW)- horizontal length between the medial and lateral canthus.

- PFH= palpebral fissure height
- PFW= palpebral fissure width
- PFI= palpebral fissure inclination

Fig. 4: Showing the palpebral fissure width.^[14]

Palpebral Fissure Angle (PFA)- the angle of the palpebral fissure height over width.

- PFH= palpebral fissure height
- PFW= palpebral fissure width
- PFI= palpebral fissure inclination
- PFA= Palpebral fissure angle

$$= \text{PFH}/\text{PFW} \times 100$$

Although palpebral fissure inclination is typically derived from the height difference between the outer and inner canthi ($Y_2 - Y_1$), this study did not capture standardized canthal height displacement. Instead, a geometric approximation of the palpebral fissure angle was computed using the vertical palpebral fissure height (PFH) and the horizontal fissure width (PFW). These measurements were obtained directly using a digital vernier caliper, and the angle was calculated as:

$$\theta = \text{DEGREES}(\arctan(\text{PFH}/\text{PFW}))$$

This method provided a consistent estimation of fissure shape that was suitable for sex-based comparative analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed to determine the significance of sex-based differences. Descriptive Statistics: Mean and standard deviation (SD) were calculated for all parameters. Inferential Statistics: Independent samples t-tests and One-way ANOVA were used to compare dimensions between males and females

and across different age groups. For the Predictive Modeling, a binary logistic regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the reliability of these measurements as markers for sex determination. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Results are presented in table 1-6 and charts.

Table 1: Gender and age group Distribution of Participants.

Gender	Frequency (%)
Male (1)	192(46.7%)
Female (2)	220(53.3%)
Total	412(100%)
Age Group (years)	Frequency
18–29	100(24.4%)
30–39	81(19.6%)
40–49	101(24.6%)
50–60	130(31.4%)
Total	412

Chart 1: Showing the distribution of age groups and gender.**Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the palpebral parameters.**

Variable	Mean \pm SEM
PFW (mm)	32.10 \pm 0.14
PFH (mm)	9.50 \pm 0.07
Palpebral angle ($^{\circ}$)	16.55 \pm 0.14
ICD (mm)	34.34 \pm 0.15
OCD (mm)	98.10 \pm 0.29

Note: PFH= palpebral fissure height, PFW= palpebral fissure width, ICD= inner Canthal distance, OCD= outer Canthal distance, mm= millimeter, SEM= standard error of mean.

Table 3: Independent samples t-test for sex differences.

Variable	t-value	df	p-value	Mean Difference (M-F)	Interpretation
PFW (mm)	0.46	410	.647	+0.13	NS
PFH (mm)	-0.25	410	.804	-0.04	NS
Palpebral angle ($^{\circ}$)	-0.51	410	.608	-0.14	NS
ICD (mm)	2.12	410	.034	+0.65	S
OCD (mm)	1.29	410	.198	+0.76	NS

Note: S= significant, NS= Not significant, PFH= palpebral fissure height, PFW= palpebral fissure width, ICD= inner Canthal distance, OCD= outer Canthal distance, mm= millimeter, df= degrees of freedom

Table 4: One-way ANOVA results (Sex as factor).

Variable	F (1,410)	p-value	Interpretation
PFW (mm)	0.21	0.647	NS
PFH (mm)	0.06	0.804	NS
Palpebral angle ($^{\circ}$)	0.26	0.608	NS
ICD (mm)	4.51	0.034	S
OCD (mm)	1.66	0.198	NS

Note: S= significant, NS= Not significant, PFH= palpebral fissure height, PFW= palpebral fissure width, ICD= inner Canthal distance, OCD= outer Canthal distance, mm= millimeter, df= degrees of freedom.

Table 5: Logical Regression Analysis.

Predictor	B	SE	Wald	p-value	Exp(B)	Interpretation
PFW (mm)	0.12	0.19	0.39	0.533	1.12	NS
PFH (mm)	-0.38	0.62	0.39	0.534	0.68	NS
Palpebral angle (°)	0.25	0.38	0.44	0.506	1.28	NS
ICD (mm)	-0.07	0.03	4.10	0.043	0.94	S
OCD (mm)	-0.02	0.02	0.99	0.319	0.98	NS

Note: S= significant, NS= Not significant, PFH= palpebral fissure height, PFW= palpebral fissure width, ICD= inner Canthal distance, OCD= outer Canthal distance, mm= millimeter, df= degrees of freedom, B= Regression Coefficient, SE= Standard Error, Exp(B) = Exponent of B, Wald= Wald's chi-square.

Table 6: One-way ANOVA results (Age groups).

Variable	F-value	df (between, within)	p-value	Interpretation
PFW (mm)	1.13	(42,369)	.280	NS
PFH (mm)	0.85	(42,369)	.741	NS
Palpebral angle (°)	0.99	(42,369)	.492	NS
ICD (mm)	0.94	(42,369)	.574	NS
OCD (mm)	1.15	(42,369)	.243	NS

Note: S= significant, NS= Not significant, PFH= palpebral fissure height, PFW= palpebral fissure width, ICD= inner Canthal distance, OCD= outer Canthal distance, mm= millimeter, df= degrees of freedom.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1, Descriptive Statistics of Age and Gender of Participants: The table presents the demographic and palpebral fissure characteristics of participants from Asari-Toru LGA, differentiated by sex. A total of 412 individuals were analyzed (192 males, 220 females). The mean age of participants was 21.4 ± 3.2 years, with a range between 16 and 28 years. Males constituted 46.6% of the sample, while females accounted for 53.4%.

Table 2, Descriptive Statistics of the palpebral fissure parameters: Descriptive analysis revealed that the mean palpebral fissure width (PFW) was 32.17 ± 2.79 mm in males and 32.04 ± 2.97 mm in females. Similarly, mean palpebral fissure height (PFH) was 9.48 ± 1.49 mm in males and 9.51 ± 1.56 mm in females. The derived palpebral angle averaged $16.47 \pm 2.73^\circ$ in males and $16.62 \pm 2.88^\circ$ in females. Overall, the descriptive statistics suggest that while males tended to have slightly larger canthal dimensions, the differences in palpebral fissure height, width, and angle were minimal. Inner canthal distance (ICD) showed slightly higher values in males (34.69 ± 3.33 mm) than in females (34.04 ± 2.89 mm), while outer canthal distance (OCD) was also higher in males (98.51 ± 6.07 mm) compared to females (97.75 ± 5.87 mm).

Table 3, Independent Samples T-Test by Sex: Independent samples t-tests were conducted to compare male and female groups across all measured variables (Table 4.2). Results revealed no statistically significant sex differences for PFW ($p = 0.647$), PFH ($p = 0.804$), palpebral angle ($p = 0.608$), or OCD ($p = 0.198$). However, a significant difference was observed in ICD ($p = 0.034$), with males having wider inner canthal distances compared to females. These findings indicate

that, in this population, ICD is the only periocular measure that demonstrates significant sexual dimorphism, while other fissure dimensions appear broadly similar between sexes.

Table 4, One-Way ANOVA by Sex: To confirm sex-related differences, one-way ANOVA was performed. Results were consistent with the t-test findings: no significant differences in PFW, PFH, palpebral angle, or OCD were observed ($p > 0.05$). Only ICD showed significant variation between males and females ($F = 4.51$, $p = 0.034$). This reinforces the conclusion that ICD is the most sexually dimorphic palpebral variable within this study population.

Table 6, One-Way ANOVA by Age Groups: An additional analysis was performed to explore whether age group contributed to variability in palpebral dimensions. ANOVA revealed that none of the measured variables (PFW, PFH, palpebral angle, ICD, OCD) differed significantly across age groups ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that, within the sampled 18–60-years age range, palpebral dimensions remain stable and are not significantly influenced by age.

Table 5, Logical Regression Analysis: A binary logistic regression was conducted to assess whether palpebral measurements could predict sex. The overall model fit was weak (Nagalkerke $R^2 = 0.02$), indicating very limited predictive power. Among the predictors, only ICD emerged as statistically significant ($p = 0.043$), with higher ICD associated with male sex. Other variables (PFW, PFH, palpebral angle, OCD) were not significant predictors ($p > 0.05$). The classification accuracy of the model was 54.9%, only marginally better than chance, suggesting that palpebral fissure variables alone are not

reliable indicators for sex classification in this population.

The present study examined sexual dimorphism in palpebral fissure dimensions among adults in Asari-Toru Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The parameters assessed included palpebral fissure width (PFW), palpebral fissure height (PFH), palpebral angle, inner canthal distance (ICD), and outer canthal distance (OCD). Although males exhibited slightly higher mean values across most parameters, only the ICD showed a statistically significant sex difference ($p = 0.034$). Other variables revealed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$), and age showed no significant influence on any measurement.

Palpebral Fissure Width (PFW)

In the present study, the mean PFW was 32.17 ± 2.79 mm in males and 32.04 ± 2.97 mm in females, showing no significant sex difference. This finding aligns with reports from Serbia^[15], India^[16], and Nigeria^[17], where no significant sexual dimorphism in PFW was observed. The minimal difference between sexes may be attributed to the high individual variability of orbital soft-tissue structures and the influence of genetic and ethnic background rather than sex hormones. Conversely, some South Indian studies^[18] reported significantly higher male PFW values, a difference possibly due to ethnic craniofacial morphology, measurement methods, and sample age range.

Palpebral Fissure Height (PFH)

The mean PFH in the present study was 9.48 ± 1.49 mm in males and 9.51 ± 1.56 mm in females, showing no significant sex difference. This pattern agrees with findings from African^[19] and Asian^[9] populations, which reported overlapping PFH values across sexes. Height of the palpebral fissure is largely determined by levator palpebrae and orbital septal structure, which exhibit minimal sexual variation. Minor differences observed across populations can be attributed to environmental factors such as exposure to sunlight, habitual squinting, and eyelid tissue elasticity.

Palpebral Angle

The mean palpebral angle recorded for the present study was $16.47^\circ \pm 2.73$ in males and $16.62^\circ \pm 2.88$ in females, indicating no significant sex difference. This agrees with findings by^[20] in a Nigerian cohort and by Farkas *et al.*^[21] internationally. The similarity between male and female palpebral angles may be due to the strong genetic determination of lateral canthal inclination, which remains relatively stable across adult life and is less influenced by sexual dimorphism. Some Asian studies have shown narrower palpebral angles in females, which may relate to regional facial contour and eyelid morphology differences.

Inner Canthal Distance (ICD)

The ICD for the present study was 34.69 ± 3.33 mm in males and 34.04 ± 2.89 mm in females, revealing a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.034$). This supports several studies in Nigerian and global contexts that report ICD as the most sexually dimorphic periocular parameter.^{[22],[23],[15]} The wider ICD in males is likely related to broader nasal bridges, greater mid-facial skeletal breadth, and androgen-driven bone development during puberty.

Notably, Benwoke *et al.*^[24] studies on the Kalabari population reported mean ICD values of 35.02 ± 2.85 mm in males and 34.41 ± 2.76 mm in females, which are comparable to those observed in the present study. Their findings further confirmed statistically significant sex differences in ICD among Kalabari adults, suggesting that inner canthal distance is a stable sexual marker within Niger Delta ethnic groups. The similarity between the Asari-Toru and Kalabari data indicates shared regional craniofacial characteristics, possibly influenced by common ancestry and environmental adaptation.

The mean ICD in the present study (34.34 ± 3.10 mm) aligns with the general West African range (34–39 mm) and exceeds values reported in Asian and European groups (28–33 mm), reflecting established interethnic craniofacial variations. Such differences are largely genetic, arising from orbital and nasal morphological adaptations characteristic of African populations.

Outer Canthal Distance (OCD)

The mean OCD for the present study was 98.51 ± 6.07 mm in males and 97.75 ± 5.87 mm in females, showing no statistically significant difference. These values correspond with ranges reported for Nigerian adults^{[25],[26]} and remain within upper African limits. Similarly, Benwoke *et al.*^[24] recorded mean OCD values of 99.24 ± 5.91 mm in Kalabari males and 98.72 ± 6.02 mm in females, demonstrating minimal sexual dimorphism and supporting the current findings.

The consistent pattern across studies suggests that the outer canthal distance (OCD) exhibits minor or no dimorphism. The absence of significant dimorphism in OCD across both Kalabari and Asari-Toru samples may be attributed to shared ethnic ancestry and craniofacial proportions characteristic of southern Nigerian populations. Minor variations among studies may result from differences in sample size, age distribution, measurement landmarks, methodology, or environmental influences during facial growth.

Collectively, the results indicate that among the palpebral fissure parameters, only inner canthal distance (ICD) demonstrates significant sexual dimorphism. All other parameters (PFW, PFH, palpebral angle, and OCD) show minimal or no sex-related differences. Logistic regression confirmed that these features have limited predictive power for sex determination (Nagelkerke $R^2 =$

0.02; classification accuracy = 54.9%). Therefore, while ICD may serve as an auxiliary indicator in anthropometric and forensic evaluations, palpebral fissure parameters alone are insufficient for reliable sex classification. The findings emphasize the importance of population-specific facial reference data to enhance diagnostic and forensic accuracy in Nigerian and African populations.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that while males exhibited slightly higher mean values across most parameters, only the Inner Canthal Distance (ICD) showed a statistically significant sex difference ($p = 0.034$). Other variables, including palpebral fissure width, height, angle, and outer canthal distance, revealed no significant sex differences ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, age showed no significant influence on any of the measured parameters within the 18–60 years range. The predictive model yielded a classification accuracy of only 54.9%, suggesting that palpebral fissure variables alone are not reliable primary indicators for sex determination in this population.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Palpebral fissure dimensions should not be used alone for sex determination in Rivers State populations, but they may be combined with other craniofacial and skeletal parameters. More studies should be carried out with larger samples, and across different ethnic groups in Nigeria, to build a stronger database of craniofacial measurements. Future research can make use of 3D imaging or digital photogrammetry to get more precise and reproducible results.

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